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My Post Graduate & Professional Research and Study on Chartered Management

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Abstract

Chartered management qualification is very important in this age of manage globalization. In chartered manager we study the different stream of management. In chartered manager we study about the buying and selling material, we study about the economic order quantity of material management. In the chartered manager we study all the aspects of material management, which is relate to production and operation management. In the chartered manager we study about the operation management with detail and study case. in the chartered manager we can learn about the utilization of resource under the principles of operation management, in operation management we study about the best location of resources and it utilization according to the needs. In the Chartered Management, we study quality control and project management

Keywords : *chartered, manager, management.*

Introduction

In the chartered manager study, we discuss quality control management, which relates to the standard of performance. In chartered management, we study about project management, in which we estimate the completion of activities in various phases of the desired project. In chartered manager study about the marketing management, in the chartered manager we study about the sales, promotion, market And segmentation and about the marketing strategies. In the chartered management we study about the marketing concept which is relate to the conceptually to marketing management. Business management is very important in this era of globalization. (DuBrin, A. J. (2009). *Essentials of management* & Koontz, H. (n.d.). *Essentials of management*. & Heizer, J., Render, B., & Munson, C. (2020). *Operations management: Sustainability and supply chain Management*.)

Literature review

In the chartered manager study we study management including planning, directing, organizing, Motivation, decision making. In chartered manager we study about the international management, in the chartered manager we discuss the various factor which is relate to the international management. In chartered manager we study about the financial and managerial accounts, in the chartered manager we discuss the accounts in detail with solution problems according to the international standards. In the chartered manager, we study labor and industrial laws and company laws. The basic purpose of law study is to implement the policies in the right direction. In the chartered manager, we study payroll management; in the chartered manager study, we learn about the payroll system. In the chartered manager, we study financial management. During the study of chartered manager, we discuss all the aspects of finance, investment, and other concepts of financial management, which are very viable in financial management. In Chartered manager we study different subjects. Financial Accounting, Managerial accounting, Business management, Financial

management, Behavior science, project management, operational management, Buying and selling material, Quality control management. (DuBrin, A. J. (2009). *Essentials of management* & Koontz, H. (n.d.). *Essentials of management*. & Heizer, J., Render, B., & Munson, C. (2020). *Operations management: Sustainability and supply chain Management*.)

Subjects study in chartered management qualification

A :Business management education

Business education is very important for one society. With the help of business education we can not enter in the era of globalization. Education is only which provide the way of progress and prosperousness. In this era of globalization we are facing many challenges. Business education is very crucial for every person. Business education provide the guide line to person, how to run the business. If we study the business education there are the many components like planning, direction, organizing and quality assurance. Business education helps how to make planning like budgeting and other financial planning. Business education provide direction regarding the human resource and organizing. Organizing is very important component of the business management. With the help of organizing, we allocate the human resource. Direction is the important part of business management in which we frame the policy and procedure of the companies related matters. Direction is the integral part of business management we design all the rules and regulations, which is correlate to the direct matter of the business. Other important part of the business education of the assurance, assurance is the important part of business education. In quality assurance we make the policy regarding the standardization of the business, with the help of quality assurance we can reach the target of the best quality assurance. We cannot ignore the importance of material and operation management. Operation management and material management is the integral part of the business operation. With the help of operation management we can achieve the target of better capacity. Business education is the more important after the scientific and technologic revolution. Business education is being included in the syllabus of every highest level education like masters and PhD. Many thesis are being conducted to day on the various topic of the business management. Many research papers are being written by the various research on the topics of the business management in various journals. Many professional institutes came in to being for the promotion of business education. Many education qualifications were introduced in the universities like MBA and BBA. Business education is the integral part of education world. If we want to achieve the goal of economic development we should promote the Business education. Business education is very essential for society. In various countries many business schools was established. Many books are published by the author. (Koontz, H. (n.d.). *Essentials of management (McGraw-Hill series in management)*. McGraw-Hill. & Drucker, P. F. (1999, March–April). *Managing oneself. Harvard Business Review*.)

B: Marketing management

Marketing Management is the importance part of our life. without marketing management we cannot achieve the target of sales. Marketing is the only way which provide the way of progress to the entire world. with the passage of time marketing management increase his credibility in the world profession. The concept of marketing management was present in the man naturally. Every body want that his product should be sold on the reasonable price, therefore we can say the marketing is the integral part of world. Economy. when we study the marketing management first we should consider the concept of segmentation. Segmentation is the vital part of our marketing management. in segmentation we examine the product with demographically. when we study the demographically concept. Segmentation concept provide which product is suitable for people of other country. Marketing segmentation give the awareness and guidance how the produce can be successful in region. The second concept of marketing management product cycle. in product cycle we generate the idea and scanning of mind. Allocate the Budget, Research and Development is the important part of product cycle. with the help of research and Development we can measure the effectiveness of product. if the research are not give good result, we can made the further steps for the improvement in the product. with the help of marketing management

we can reach the good result of the product development. Commercialization is the important part of marketing management with the help of commercialization of product we can achieve the target of sales. Marketing management guide which can be situation in the marketing regarding the launching of product. There are a lot of situations are faced in the marketing. Perfect competition. In perfect competition every one want to achieve the market with the help of manipulation of price, this situation is very important for seller, because he want gain in the market. Second phase of marketing competition is monopolist competition, in monopolist competition some seller are agree on such settlement, in monopolistic competition not allow others to enter in the market. Very important thing is that antidumping approach. In which some body enter in the market with the reduce the price which is very comparatively low as compare to the other sellers. Very important part of the marketing management is that promotion of sales. Marketing management provide the tools how to increase of sales through Advertising, promotion, Marketing Management provide the way how the product can be promoted through various ways. Marketing Mix are the importance concept of marketing management. Product, place, price promotion. These are very viable tools of marketing. When we adopt this approach we can get the success in the marketing regarding the achievement of sales and promotion. Thus we can say that the marketing management is the important part of our life. If can get the achievement we can adopt the good marketing strategy and models. Marketing Management is the very fine tool for every body. (Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2006). *Marketing management (12th ed.)*).

C: Human resources management.

Human resource is the important part of our world. With the help of human resource we cannot achieve the goal of development in human life. Before the some years the human resource department is not important. But in the era of globalization the human resource became the important department. After the scientific revolution the human resource is very important, human resource is very important in this era of globalization. Human resource management is directly link to human physiology. Human resource management is directly link with the Business management. Human resource management guide us in many areas of human development. Human resource management provide the way how to utilize the human talent according to target. Human resource management study is very important student. Human resource management are being teaches in every university and business school. (Flippo, E. B. (1980). *Personnel management (6th ed.)*. McGraw-Hill.)

D: Economics

Economics qualifications are base of every society. Economics is consist on various school of thought. Before some deceds the some countries faced depression and inflation, because of good economist and good economic education we came over all economic problems. Economics education is very vital for every socitey. Economics education are teaching approximately are taught in every university of world. It is the need of hour that we should get the economics education. Economics education can bring the social revolution in any society. With the help of good economic system we can bring the financial discipline in our socitey. Financial institute are the back bone of economy. qualified economist run the system very wall. Economist is the only person which can bring the social revolution in the society. (Mankiw, N. G. (2021). *Principles of Economics*).

E: Supply chain management

Supply chain management is the important way and subject in this era of globalization, with out supply chain management the concept of accuracy is not possible. The actual meaning of supply chain management the supply of material should reach to actual customer. Supply chain is possible only with the help of estimation of material needs and requirement. In the concept of supply chain management we estimate the economic order quantity, with the help of economic order quantity we can estimate the economic order quantity, which is needed by the business. The basic purpose of supply chain is to maintain the quantity of material in the different situation. We can estimate how the material is needed in the different situations. Supply chain management give

lesson how the material can reach the actual place. The basic factor in the supply chain management that the material should reach in the reasonable time. In such cases when the material reach in the reasonable time the supply chain management will be the successful. Supply chain management is very important in the operation and production management. Operation and production can be successfully with the help of supply chain management. In the Japan the supply chain management is very successfully because of disaster management. Disaster management can be possible with the help of supply chain management. (Heizer, J., Render, B., & Munson, C. (2020). *Operations management: Sustainability and supply chain management*).

Research regarding chartered management

I conducted the qualitative and quantitative research

My hypothesis proved correct that chartered management qualifications is very effective for professional.

Table.

Category.	yes.	No
Accountant	3.	0
MBA.	4	0
M.Com.	5.	0

Table 2:

Cetogory	Yes.	No
Economist.	4.	0
Tax consultant	5.	0
Accountant.	6.	0

The result of research that Chartered manager is very good professional qualifications.

Statement of acknowledgemt

I wrote this research paper with out any help. Finally I completed my study regarding the chartered management. because of my professional qualifications in chartered manager, I completed my research in chartered manager.

Conclusion Chartered management study is very important in the era of globalization and development. with the help of chartered management study we can achieve the target of growth and stability. Chartered manager is the beneficial status for the organization. with the help of chartered manager we can use the viable techniques for the resolve of problems. The person who have the status of chartered manager he can resolve all the issues which is relate to operation management and marketing management and supply chain management. Chartered management status provide the guideline how to develop the management style. Holder of the chartered management qualifications can prove the very good for the organization. Chartered management holder design the planning according the demand of organization. Specially in human resources management the chartered manager play the dynamic role regarding the implementation of human resources management. Thus we can say that chartered management qualifications prove very beneficial for organization.

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